

PARTIALLY OBSERVABLE MODEL-BASED LEARNING FOR ISAC RESOURCE ALLOCATION

Petteri Pulkkinen^{†}, Visa Koivunen^{*}*

^{*}Department of Information and Communications Engineering, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland

[†]Saab Finland Oy, Helsinki, Finland

ABSTRACT

This paper considers resource allocation problems for integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) systems operating in dynamic shared spectrum scenarios. Specifically, the paper proposes a new Model-Based Online Learning (MBOL) method that accounts for partial observability caused by noisy observations. First, the approach converts the partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) to the equivalent belief state Markov decision process (MDP). Then, the state prediction model is learned from the sensor observations. A loss correction approach is introduced to solve the model learning problem under partial observability. The proposed approach is evaluated in allocating subcarriers and their powers to communications and sensing tasks in multicarrier ISAC systems. The simulations demonstrate improved performance in partially observable settings.

Index Terms— noisy labels, reinforcement learning, partially observable Markov decision process, model-based online learning

1. INTRODUCTION

A key new technology in the emerging 6G wireless systems is integrating radio frequency (RF) sensing with communications [1]. Integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) systems reduce the overall system cost and power consumption as well as mitigate the congestion in the radio spectrum. We consider dynamic shared spectrum scenarios where the spectrum varies rapidly in time-frequency-space dimensions. To learn and adapt in such scenarios, resource allocation methods based on reinforcement learning [2] and online convex optimization [3] are developed that autonomously improve performance in real-time using the gained experiences.

In the context of ISAC systems, the online (reinforcement) learning methods can be coarsely categorized into model-free [4–11] and model-based [12, 13] methods. The Model-Free Online Learning (MFOL) methods learn decision-making policies directly from experience by trial and error. These methods can be data inefficient, especially when the cardinality of the decision space is large, as typically is the case in ISAC systems. In contrast, Model-Based Online Learning (MBOL) methods have been proposed [12, 13] to make learning algorithms more explainable and sample-efficient by utilizing the rich structural information on communications, sensing systems, and radio environments.

Previous MBOL methods model the spectrum state using discrete states (e.g., channel occupied or idle) [12] or quantized state information [13]. For the models proposed in [12, 13], the state transition

distributions can be learned using the multiclass logistic regression (MLR) method. However, in realistic scenarios, the spectrum state observations are noisy, making considering the partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) model necessary. In [12], partial observability was briefly considered for two state channel models where each channel is considered either occupied or idle, while in [13], a fully observable scenario was assumed.

This paper proposes new methods that generalize the previously proposed MBOL methods [12, 13] to account for partial observability of the spectrum. The proposed approach is composed of two main components. First, the problem is converted to a belief state Markov decision process (MDP) using memory. Then, this memory is fed into the learned state prediction model that predicts the probability distribution of the next state. We show that the proposed model learning problem is related to learning from noisy labels in classification problems [14], which is a widely studied problem in machine learning (see [14] and references therein). In the considered ISAC problem, the noisy labels (i.e., the target states for prediction) are assessed based on sensor observations. Thus, the problem can be solved using the loss correction methods proposed in [15]. The methods are demonstrated in allocating subcarriers and their powers to sensing and communications functions in dynamic spectrum environments.

Contributions of this paper are the following: (i) We generalize our previous approaches in [12, 13] to account for partial observability. We show that the problem relates to learning classifiers with partially observable labels [14]. (ii) The proposed and baseline methods are compared in simulations. The empirical results show that the proposed forward correction method paired with long short-term memory (LSTM) outperforms the baselines in partially observable settings. Furthermore, the performance of the ISAC system is practically unaffected by the forward correction method in comparison to the oracle method.

2. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

We consider a resource allocation problem where a colocated multicarrier ISAC system operates in the same spectrum bands with cooperative and non-cooperative sensing or communications systems and adversarial systems. The system optimizes performance by adaptively allocating frequency and power resources for sensing and communication functions.

2.1. Signal model

We employ a signal model similar to [11, 13] for a multicarrier ISAC system with N sub-carriers. A quasi-stationary model is assumed

where statistics remain wide-sense stationary (WSS) over the observation period. Each observation period is associated with a time slot index $k \in \mathbb{N}$. During one time slot, multiple pulses/symbols may be transmitted. We use the superscripts $f \in \{r, c\}$ to distinguish between the sensing and communications functions, respectively.

We approximate the linear time-domain convolutions of the channel as circular convolutions, which is a valid approximation when N is large or a cyclic prefix is employed [16, 17]. Thus, we may write the received pulse/symbol for the function $f \in \{r, c\}$ and slot $k \in \mathbb{N}$ in the *frequency domain* as follows

$$\mathbf{r}_k^f = (\mathbf{B}_k^r + \mathbf{B}_k^c) \mathbf{h}_k^f + \mathbf{v}_k^f \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_k^f \in \mathbb{C}^N$ is the channel with covariance matrix \mathbf{G}_k^f , $\mathbf{B}_k^r \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{B}_k^c \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ are diagonal matrices of the transmitted sensing and communications code, respectively, and $\mathbf{v}_k^f \in \mathbb{C}^N$ is the noise plus interference with covariance matrix \mathbf{N}_k^f . Due to the WSS assumption, the frequency domain covariance matrices \mathbf{G}_k^f and \mathbf{N}_k^f are well approximated as diagonal matrices due to the circulant approximations in the time domain. We use the shorthand notation $\mathbf{g}_k^f := \text{diag}(\mathbf{G}_k^f)$. In addition, the diagonal elements of \mathbf{N}_k^f are composed as follows

$$\mathbf{n}_k^f := \text{diag}(\mathbf{N}_k^f) = \mathbf{n}_k^{\text{co} \rightarrow f} + \mathbf{n}_k^{\text{nc} \rightarrow f} + \sigma^2 \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_k^{\text{co} \rightarrow f}$ denotes the experienced interference from the cooperative systems, $\mathbf{n}_k^{\text{nc} \rightarrow f}$ denotes the (un)intentional interferences from non-cooperative and adversarial users, and σ^2 denotes the noise.

2.2. POMDP formulation

We extend the MDP formulation in [13] to consider the partially observable scenario. The action $\mathbf{a}_k \in \mathcal{A}$ comprises the allocation of transmission power $\mathbf{p}_k \in \Delta^N$ and the sub-carrier assignments $\mathbf{w}_k \in \{r, c\}^N$ where Δ^N is the scaled simplex such that elements in \mathbf{p}_k sum up to total power P_{tot} . We assume that $\mathbf{n}_k^{\text{co} \rightarrow f}$ can be obtained as side information via cooperation, and the channel statistics \mathbf{g}_k^f vary slowly. However, the experienced interferences from the adversarial and non-cooperative systems can vary rapidly from slot to slot; thus, we use MDP state $\mathbf{s}_k^f = \mathbf{n}_k^{\text{nc} \rightarrow f}$ to model it. The observations $\mathbf{z}_k^f \in \mathcal{Z}$ follow the observation model

$$h(\mathbf{z}_k^f | \mathbf{s}_k^f) := \Pr(Z_k^f = \mathbf{z}_k^f | S_k^f = \mathbf{s}_k^f) \quad (3)$$

which is assumed to be known. Unlike in general POMDPs, the observation is assumed to be independent of the action. This is because we assume signal-free noise and interference measurements in the frequency domain denoted by the vector $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{k,t}^f \in \mathbb{C}^N$ where $t \in [T] := \{1, \dots, T\}$ is the sample index during observation slot k and the number of samples in each slot is T . The actual observation for all $i \in [N]$ is defined as follows

$$z_{k,i}^f = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T |\tilde{v}_{k,t,i}^f|^2 \quad (4)$$

where $z_{k,i}^f$ and $\tilde{v}_{k,t,i}^f$ denote the i th elements of \mathbf{z}_k^f and $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{k,t}^f$, respectively. Note, $|\tilde{v}_{k,t,i}^f|^2$ is exponentially distributed with the rate $1/n_{k,i}^f$, and the sum of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) exponential variables obeys gamma distribution. Thus, $z_{k,i}^f$ obeys Gamma distribution with shape T and rate $T/n_{k,i}^f$.

The optimization objective is to maximize the average sensing mutual information (MI) with respect to constraint on the average communications MI, or vice versa. The sensing or communications MI [18] can be written as follows

$$u(\mathbf{s}_{k+1}^f, \mathbf{a}_k) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}_{\{w_{k,i}=f\}} \log \left(1 + \frac{g_{k+1,i}^f p_{k,i}}{n_{k+1,i}^f} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $w_{k,i}$, $g_{k+1,i}^f$, $n_{k+1,i}^f$ and $p_{k,i}$ correspond to the i th components of the vectors \mathbf{w}_k , \mathbf{g}_{k+1}^f , \mathbf{n}_{k+1}^f and \mathbf{p}_k , respectively.

3. PARTIALLY OBSERVABLE MODEL-BASED LEARNING

This section introduces an MBOL algorithm that can be used to solve the partially observable resource allocation problem introduced in Section 2. The MBOL methods [12, 13] refer to algorithms that learn the unknown parameters of the model in real-time and employ a controller that optimizes actions (resource allocations) based on the learned model.

3.1. Interference model

We drop the superscript $f \in \{r, c\}$ to simplify the notation because the sensing and communications models are assumed decoupled. The MBOL method learns a prediction model $T_\theta(\mathbf{s}_{k+1} | \mathbf{x}_k) = \Pr(S_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_{k+1} | X_k = \mathbf{x}_k)$ where $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathcal{X}$ represents the memory of the ISAC system and $\theta \in \Theta$ are the parameters to be learned. The memory is updated recursively as follows

$$\mathbf{x}_k = g_\theta(\mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{a}_{k-1}, \mathbf{x}_{k-1}), \quad (6)$$

where the function $g_\theta : \mathcal{Z} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ can be, for example, a recursive neural network (RNN) or a finite windowing function that records a finite number of previous observations $\mathbf{z} \in \mathcal{Z}$ and actions $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$. The vector \mathbf{x}_k is assumed to contain relevant information about the previous observations and actions, making it equivalent to the belief state of the POMDP.

Replacing the fully observable state \mathbf{s}_k by the memory \mathbf{x}_k , the state prediction model from [13] can be extended as follows

$$T_\theta(\mathbf{s}_{k+1} | \mathbf{x}_k) = \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^L [\phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_k, \theta)]^{\mathbb{1}_{\{s_{k+1,i}=\sigma_j^2\}}} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{\{\cdot\}}$ is the indicator function and σ_j^2 for all $j \in [L]$ are the L predetermined interference levels for quantization. The functions $\phi_{i,j}$ for all $i \in [N]$ and $j \in [L]$ correspond the learned probability masses and are defined as follows

$$\phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_k, \theta) = \frac{\exp \psi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_k, \theta)}{\sum_{l=1}^L \exp \psi_{i,l}(\mathbf{x}_k, \theta)} \quad (8)$$

where $\psi : \mathcal{X} \times \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N \times L}$ can be any parametric function approximator.

In the fully observable setting model parameters $\theta \in \Theta$ are learned by minimizing the cross-entropy loss [13]

$$L(\theta) = -\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{x}_{k-1}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^L Y_{k,i,j} \log \phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \theta) \right] \quad (9)$$

where $Y_{k,i,j} = \mathbb{1}_{\{s_{k,i}=\sigma_j^2\}}$ is the quantized interference level and $\mathbf{Y}_k \in \mathcal{Y}$ denotes the matrix composed of $Y_{k,i,j}$ for all $i \in [N]$ and $j \in [L]$. The problem of \mathbf{Y}_k being unobservable will be addressed by the methods proposed in Section 3.3.

3.2. The controller algorithm

The considered MBOL algorithm employs the controller proposed in [13] to allocate resources. A brief overview of the algorithm is given in this paper; a more detailed description can be found in [13].

Without loss of generality, this paper considers the optimization problem where sensing performance is maximized under communication rate constraints. At each time slot $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the controller optimizes the following myopic optimization problem

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} J_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_k^r, \mathbf{a}) \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } J_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_k^c, \mathbf{a}) \geq C \quad (10b)$$

where $J_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_k^f, \mathbf{a}) = \mathbb{E}_{T_{\theta}} [u(\mathbf{s}_{k+1}^f, \mathbf{a}_k) | \mathbf{x}_k^f, \mathbf{a}_k]$ is the expected MI under the learned model T_{θ} for $f \in \{r, c\}$. The expectation can be written in closed form as follows

$$J_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_k^f, \mathbf{a}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^L \mathbb{1}_{\{w_{k,i}=f\}} \phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_k^f, \theta) \log \left(1 + \frac{g_{k+1,i}^f}{n_{k+1,i}^{co \rightarrow f} + \sigma_j^2 + \sigma^2} p_{k,i} \right). \quad (11)$$

Due to the non-convexity of the problem, the controller solves it in three stages. First, it assigns all sub-channels for communications and optimizes the power allocation by maximizing $J_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_k^c, \mathbf{a})$. Then, it minimizes the number of sub-carriers and the required power subject to constraint in (10b). Lastly, the remaining sub-carriers and power budget are used to maximize sensing performance in (10a).

3.3. Proposed loss functions for model learning

We propose forward and backward loss correction methods, inspired by [15], to address the partially observed model learning. Although the backward method exhibits high gradient variance due to matrix inversion, it is included to align with a similar approach in [15].

3.3.1. Backward correction method

The model loss in (9) can be effectively optimized by designing an unbiased gradient estimator. To do that, we can replace \mathbf{Y}_k with a function $G : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N \times L}$ to be designed. For unbiasedness, it is required that $\mathbb{E}[G_i(\mathbf{z}_k) | s_{k,i} = \sigma_j^2] = \mathbf{e}_j$ for all $i \in [N]$ and $j \in [L]$ where G_i denotes the i th row of the output of function G , and \mathbf{e}_j is the j th standard unit vector. We design the function G by first employing a maximum likelihood (ML) method to estimate \mathbf{Y}_k from the measurement \mathbf{z}_k , and then the estimates will be weighted linearly.

The ML-based detector computes the likelihood of hypotheses $h(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{Y}_k)$ for all $\mathbf{Y}_k \in \mathcal{Y}$, and the hypothesis with the highest likelihood is chosen. Since the interference plus noise statistics are assumed to be independent among the sub-channels, we can compute the ML detections for each channel independently to save computation. Thus, we assign detectors D_i for all sub-channels $i \in [N]$, outputting one-hot encoded vectors indicating the detections.

After the noisy detections have been made, the resulting unbiased estimator is similar to the backward correction method in [15]. The unbiased gradient estimator can be written as follows

$$\hat{\nabla}_{\theta} L(\theta) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^L [(\mathbf{U}_i^{-1})^T D_i(\mathbf{z}_k)]_j \nabla_{\theta} \log \phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \theta) \quad (12)$$

Table 1: Simulation parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
# of subcarriers	N	16
Capacity req.	C	3
Power	P_{tot}	3
Ch. gain	$g_i \forall i \in [N]$	1e-2
Noise power	σ^2	1e-3
# of interf. levels	L	6 (easy), 16 (difficult)
# of sig.-free meas.	T	1
# of interf. sources		12

where \mathbf{U}_i is the confusion matrix of the detector D_i , which can be computed offline since the measurement model is known. The matrix \mathbf{U}_i is well-conditioned when the observation densities are easily distinguishable given the different quantized states. However, the condition number may be large for difficult observation models, inevitably increasing the gradient estimator variance.

3.3.2. Forward correction method

The forward correction method proposed in [15] could be employed to deal with the noisy estimates of the detector D introduced in Section 3.3.1. However, we can completely avoid the need for using the detector. This is because the forward method is motivated by maximizing the likelihood of observations written as follows

$$\hat{L}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{x}_{k-1}} [\log \Pr(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1})] \quad (13)$$

where we sample \mathbf{z}_k and \mathbf{x}_{k-1} from their joint distribution. The likelihood of an observation given our model can be written as follows

$$\Pr(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s}_k \in \mathcal{S}} h(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{s}_k) T_{\theta}(\mathbf{s}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}) \quad (14)$$

where we have the known observation density function h and the modeled state prediction probability T_{θ} . Thus, the forward corrected loss function can be written as follows

$$\hat{L}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{x}_{k-1}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \log \sum_{j=1}^L h_i(z_{k,i} | \sigma_j^2) \phi_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \theta) \right] \quad (15)$$

where the predicted state probabilities are weighted by the observation likelihoods.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The simulation environment used for the numerical evaluation is composed as follows. We simulate multiple interference sources where a single source is modeled using two Markov chains. One Markov chain determines the probabilities for changing sub-channels; the other models the interference power between subsequent time slots. The interference levels are the same as the quantization levels used by the MBOL algorithm. Table 1 shows the simulation parameters.

We determine the quantized interference levels using the interference-plus-noise-to-noise ratio (INNR) defined as

$$\text{INNR} := 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{n^{\text{nc} \rightarrow \text{f}} + \sigma^2}{\sigma^2} \right).$$

The minimum value for INNR is 0 dB, indicating no interference, and the maximum value is set to 30 dB. We select the interference levels such that the INNR values are evenly spaced on a decibel scale.

Table 2: Performance with different architectures.

Architecture	MI (sensing)	MI (comms.)	Model loss
LSTM	6.71	3.0	2.93
Non-linear W.	6.55	2.96	2.98
Linear W.	6.63	2.9	3.02
Linear	6.07	3.04	3.06
Non-linear	6.08	2.99	3.07

The easy simulation scenario refers to the case where interference levels are quantized to 6 levels such that the interval between two subsequent INNRS is 6dB. The difficult case refers to 16 levels with an interval of 2 dB.

4.1. Architecture comparison

We evaluate different architectures for the memory g_θ in (6) and for the function approximator $\psi_{i,j}$ in (8). The three memory architectures are (i) a single-layered LSTM with an output size of 64 units, (ii) windowed memory with a fixed window size of 8, and (iii) a no-memory approach relying solely on the latest observation. The LSTM-based memory is exclusively paired with the non-linear prediction model implemented as a feedforward neural network with a single hidden layer of 64 units and rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation. The windowed and no-memory approaches are both paired with linear and non-linear prediction models. Thus, there are five different architectures in total. Furthermore, all methods use the ML detector introduced in Section 3.3.1 as an input mapping and are trained using Adam [19] optimizer with its suggested default parameters.

The algorithms are trained in a batch mode where the batch size is 16 samples, and we train for five epochs. The training dataset size is 100×10^3 samples, and the test dataset has 20×10^3 samples. To evaluate the architecture, we assume that the inputs to the memory are noisy, but the targets \mathbf{Y}_k in (9) are fully observed. The loss correction methods are evaluated in Section 4.2.

Table 2 shows the performance with the different architectures. We see that LSTM-based approach achieves the highest sensing performance while also satisfying the constraint. The difference between the windowed linear and non-linear approaches is not large. However, the non-linear method has a slightly smaller model loss and is closer to satisfying the constraint. The methods using no memory perform the weakest in terms of model loss and sensing performance. The difference between linear and non-linear methods is small in this case.

4.2. Loss correction comparison

This section compares the backward and forward correction methods proposed in Section 3.3 using the LSTM-based architecture that was found to perform the best in Section 4.1. The same training and test datasets as in Section 4.1 are used. However, we sequentially train the algorithms to evaluate performance in a realistic online learning setting where the model is updated as new data is available.

Fig. 1a shows results in the easy simulation scenario, where all methods improve sensing performance while meeting communication constraints. The backward method, however, converges slowly due to increased variance, performing worse than the noisy method without correction. In contrast, the forward method converges nearly as fast as the oracle method, which has full access to target states (similarly as was the case in Section 4.1). This indicates the forward correction effectively optimizes the cross-entropy loss function (9). Note that

Fig. 1: Comparison of the loss correction methods. The forward correction achieves the MI levels of the oracle in (a) and (b). The backward method performs poorly in terms of (a) slow convergence and (b) divergence due to an ill-conditioned confusion matrix.

these simulations are for $T = 1$, and a smaller gap is expected between forward and noisy methods for larger $T > 1$.

Fig. 1b shows the performance in the difficult scenario where the quantization grid is finer. In this scenario, the condition number of the confusion matrix is considerably large. Therefore, the backward method fails miserably to converge since the variance of gradient estimates is greatly increased. Thus, in Fig. 1b, the backward method assigns all subcarriers for communications. However, the forward method converges approximately as fast as the oracle method and improves the performance upon using only the noisy detector estimates. This suggests that the forward correction method is very suitable for the partially observable scenarios.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper considers the problem of resource allocation in integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) systems operating in dynamic shared spectrum environments. We extend our previous Model-Based Online Learning (MBOL) methods to handle partial observability to improve performance in scenarios where only substantially noisy estimates of the spectrum state are available. We show that the proposed long short-term memory (LSTM) architecture and forward correction method improve the performance significantly and satisfy the imposed communication rate constraints in partially observable settings. Furthermore, the simulation results show that when the proposed forward loss correction method is used, the performance and data efficiency of the MBOL method are almost identical to the oracle method.

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